

Achieving state independence in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: *This article describes news published in newspapers about the independence of Uzbekistan and the joy of the holiday of that time.*

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“Children born on Independence Day will be given strollers and 1000 soums,” “Let it be true that the Uzbeks sowed their seeds!” - says the newspapers published after the declaration of independence! On August 31, 1991, at the VI session of the Supreme Council, Uzbekistan was declared independent. What did the Uzbek press write on this day and on the eve of the 1st anniversary of independence?

In 1991, most of the articles published in newspapers such as Uzbekistan Ovozi, Ishanch, Qishloq Haqiqiti and Family and Society read by Uzbeks said that people welcomed independence with great hope and that independence was for them useful. they seem to believe that it gives life.

The newspaper "Council of Uzbekistan" (now "Voice of Uzbekistan"), which at that time was a publication of the Communist Party, published a message on its front page on Saturday, August 31, 1991, entitled "Historic Day Today." It is reported that the opening of the sixth extraordinary session of the Supreme Council of the Uzbek SSR will take place at 10 o'clock on August 31 in Tashkent. At this

time, the republics of the former Soviet Union, one after another, began to declare their independence. It's Uzbekistan's turn. Therefore, they write that the deputies came to this session in “high spirits.” “For the first time, they will discuss the historical issue of legalizing the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, realizing the noble dream of the people, lighting the lamp of hope for tomorrow. May God bless our leaders who listened to the will of the people and obeyed their hearts, the representatives of thousands of voters in the Supreme Council and the creators of this historic day,” the newspaper reports.

From September 1, 1991, the name of the newspaper “Council of Uzbekistan” will be changed to “Voice of Uzbekistan”, and the inscription “Hello, Independent Uzbekistan” will be published on the main page.

This issue will also contain information about the 6th meeting, convened 1 day ago. Deputies accept the declaration of the Oliy Kengash on the independence of the republican state, and according to the corresponding decision, the name of the Uzbek SSR will be changed to the Republic of Uzbekistan. From this day forward, Independence Day will be celebrated and considered a holiday. The Supreme Council, after an article-by-article discussion, adopted the Law on State Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Islam Karimov's speech was announced on the front page of the newspaper. The speech begins like this: “Dear comrades, my compatriots! Due to the coup d'etat that took place on August 19-21, the country plunged into a terrible whirlpool of destruction. A group of people who declared themselves the State Committee for the State of Emergency in the USSR wanted to cause unprecedented suffering to millions of people... They were frightened by the fact that the republics sought to remain independent states. They realized that if the government gets out of control, no one will need them...”

Below the page is printed the poem “Sun of Justice” by Abdulla Oripov.

Has the happy wind of justice blown?
Has the truth finally accepted the call of our people?
Have the days you've been waiting for for many years arrived?
Let it be true that the sun touched our shoulders!
Let it be true that the Uzbek sowed his seed!

According to the newspaper, Karimov will meet with journalists after the sixth meeting. There he met with a Washington Post reporter and other local reporters and answered their questions. One of the questions was related to how Uzbekistan manages its gold mines. Karimov responded that the gold and silver procured at the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine are transferred to the republic, and if the central government is against it, then there is a question of transferring the gold from the Zarafshan Combine into the hands of the people of the republic. will also arise.

The issue of the newspaper “Ishanch” dated August 31, 1992 summed up the results of the first anniversary of Independence. They say that people go to Independence Square to celebrate the holiday. Bori Allamurodovich, then chairman of the Trade Union of Uzbekistan, told the journalist about independence: “Independence Day of the republic has become the most dear, national holiday of each of us, each family. That's why you feel the excitement in people's hearts...”

In the same issue of the newspaper, writer Pirimkul Kadyrov, who at that time was the chairman of the committee on interethnic relations, language and culture of the Supreme Council, explains in detail how the coat of arms and flag, which are symbols of independence, are constructed, and how he encountered resistance when adopting the symbols: . . . We found here the beautiful blue color of Amir Temur’s flag and the clear green image of the Ghaznavid flag, made copies of them and

showed them to people's deputies during the session. Academician A. Askarov and the famous historian B. Akhmedov spoke on television and explained to the general public various alternative versions of the flag and coat of arms..."

Bakhtiyor Boranov, a teacher at school No. 9 in the Nurata district of Navoi, says: "We believe that if the citizens of our independent republic do not succumb to excessive emotions and patiently carry out the tasks assigned to them, we will achieve the desired goal. "

The Declaration of the 6th Session of Independence and Karimov's speech were also printed on the front page of the Qishloq Haqiqiti newspaper, another publication of the Central Committee of the Communist Party at the time. On the next pages of the newspaper an article by the people's writer of Uzbekistan Hamid Gulam "Oshal kun keldi" will be published.

"From this day of this year, that is, from this day, our land, nature, subsoil, all structures and enterprises, all the treasures created by our people will be transferred to our republic. From all our roads, rivers and lakes, from animals and plants to water and air railways - everything belongs to us, our people... Our foreign economic relations will be at our disposal, we will have access to the city markets that we will build. By the way, we will educate our children at the most prestigious universities in the world..."

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